

The Clerk to the Committee
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
Office of Parliament,
Osu
Accra

28 September 2021

Dear Sir/Madam(s)
This document explains my objections to the Bill.

INTRODUCTION:

The "Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values" Bill is a misnomer.

I will explain this below and how it is an extremely misguided and undereducated Bill, based on myths, hate, prejudice and fear. This is 21st Century Ghana, which should not be a nation of ignorance, hate, superstition and fear. These should have been left behind when Ghana won her independence over 60 years ago. There is really nothing to fear from gays, lesbians, bi/pansexuals, asexuals, transgender or intersex people. Spend time with them to listen and see for yourselves.

Hereafter, I will refer to LGBPTIA+ people as Gender, Sex and Orientation Minorities (GSOMs) in order to be fully inclusive while avoiding ever-growing lettering such as that which the Billmakers have proposed. Use of the term "trans" is intended to mean transgender.

PART 1:

I undertook a research project some years ago on transgender issues and learnt a lot. It required learning about L, G, B, P and I people. They go through so much emotionally and often are subject to bullying, rape, street harassment, job discrimination etc. Conversely, you don't see trans people behave in such inexcusable ways towards the cisgender public so trans people are not the problem. The impact of these hateful actions are higher rates of stress, anxiety, depression, self-harm, addiction and suicide and these of course must be prevented with kindness and love. It is immoral to hurt people in these ways, causing them to become suicidal. Accepting that there'll always be a few people who are "different" and letting them be, without harassment or discrimination helps them and society significantly.

Furthermore, my studies revealed and debunked a number of myths so let it be clear that:

- Transgender is not a form of gayness.

Gayness and being transgender are not a "vice". That would be like calling heterosexual relations and all genders a "vice". Gayness and being transgender are simply how God created some people. He makes every person unique.

- Intersex is a biological fact and sex category, not the same as being

transgender.

- Being transgender is not a choice (nor is being gay, bi, asexual etc).
 - It is not disobedience or nonconformity.
 - Cross-dressing doesn't necessarily mean transgender. Sometimes it's practicality, preference, comfort or entertainment (eg Drag as a variety of clowning/pantomime). It's crazy to ban such things.
 - Transgender people exist naturally in every part of the world and throughout history.
 - - Many ancient cultures accepted gay and pansexual relations and even transgender albeit by different names. Some managed to resist homophobic, transphobic pressure from the West.
 - It is not known why some people are trans. However it is known that male or female sex chromosomes are determined at conception whereas the maleness or femaleness of the brain develops at a later stage in foetal development and the genitalia later still. The mother's hormones at a particular stage in pregnancy may influence how the latter two develop, through no fault of her own. Therefore a plausible theory is of developing a brain more like the opposite sex to one's chromosomes and/or genitalia.
- Another possible theory is one of Chimerism: the fusion of 2 fraternal twins' eggs into one in early days of pregnancy (so one child who was originally two).
- - Development of gender identity happens later still, usually complete by 3-5 years of age. It is innate, not created by "influence". Children know who they are inside even if they do not know about the organs of the opposite sex. The child's inner sense of gender needs to be affirmed for positive mental development, regardless of whether it matches their sex. Otherwise, confusion and deeper problems arise. If their identity is a mixture of both, so be it and let it be affirmed. If their identity doesn't develop, let them be and identify whatever ways feel comfortable, in order to help their mental state be more stable.

Some other areas of confusion necessary to point out are:

- Not every gay individual is sexually active. Gayness is a part of one's being, not an action, therefore cannot be a crime or disease.
- Non-straight sexual orientation is not a "lifestyle choice" or a "preference". It is an orientation, a way one is created, just like being naturally left-handed. Different, not wrong or defective.
- Bi- and pan-sexuality are not about promiscuity or confusion.
- GSOMs having access to sexual healthcare, nonjudgmental advice and condoms etc makes it much safer, saves lives and reduces sexually transmitted disease in both gay and straight alike.
- GSOMs people are nothing new or different. They are our brothers and sisters, aunties and uncles, in every walk of life and inevitably some politicians.
- Some proponents of anti-gay attitudes are actually trying to hide that they themselves are gay.
- There is no plausible scientific or religious evidence for "conversion therapy". However there is much evidence of its harms.
- You can be 99% heterosexual, 98% heterosexual and so on. So if you are 98%

and enjoyed one homosexual encounter then went back to heterosexual relations, that doesn't mean you "overcame" homosexuality, it's simply an aspect of your predominantly-straight sexuality.

Perceived Threat:

- GSOM are really not the threat some people fear. They are more likely to be victims not abusers.
- GSOMs do not wish to "convert" anyone. Each of you know you can't change the fact you're straight!
- GSOMs can't "influence" the youth to become gay. That's illogical. If it were true, they all would be straight because all GSOMs grow up surrounded by mostly cisgender, straight people.
- - GSOMs come from straight, cisgender families whereas those with gay parents are usually straight!
- "The Gay Agenda" is fake, a ruse designed to scare you and it's working! The only "agenda" GSOMs really have is actually to make things safer for all regardless of gender, sex or orientation.
- Homosexuality and other GSOMs are nothing to do with paedophilia. Gay men aren't the ones raping daughters of Ghana or marrying them off at 13.
- - Most paedophiles are straight. Some may happen to be gay, bi or trans but that's separate coincidence. Send child abusers to jail for abuse, not their gender or orientation. Abuse is abuse. The gender of the victim or abuser is irrelevant.
- Rejecting this Bill won't magically make gay marriage legal.
- GSOMs have always been and will always be in the minority. They haven't harmed previous generations and won't harm the present or next. They won't and can't "take over" so there's nothing to fear in terms of Ghanaians' ability to procreate.
- Their purpose is not to harm anyone. If a small proportion act angrily, know that they are being provoked and treated far worse. To label them intolerant for getting angry and upset is gaslighting. To label them as aggressive based on the actions of a few is acting exactly the immature way corrupt whites treat African-Americans! Many Black neighbourhoods in the USA do have higher rate of crime, violence, drugs, prostitution etc. Does this mean Black people are the problem? No! It's the result of oppression, just like with the GSOMs.

PART 2:

The Bill is Unconstitutional:

- It threatens human rights on many levels, most especially the right to one's life and safety.

I sincerely hope his Excellency, Mr President Akufo-Addo can see that, as he is a particularly intelligent and articulate leader.

This Bill Threatens Family Values:

- Family values include unconditional love, guidance, protection and support. The Bill would encourage the trashing of these vital values, breaking of families and leaving GSOM people without family, a basic social unit. This would likely increase social problems, crime, suicide, addictions etc.

The Bill Threatens Women's (and Men's!) Rights:

- Members of the public, police and judiciary would likely interpret "gender norms" in all sorts of ways and create paranoia around what may be perceived as "nonconformity"

threatening:

women who wear trousers,

women who do male-dominated jobs to support their families,

Women who study male-dominated areas,

women who are strong etc.

Men with talents for nursing, fashion, hairdressing, make-up, secretarial work etc

Unmarried individuals.

Do these Billmakers want to weaken and diminish Ghanaian women into fearful, weak creatures who remain solely in the home?

Will men have to fear wearing traditional dress if it is not trousers, thus disposing of more aspects of Ghanaian culture?

- Might my friend and I be accused of lesbianism whenever I stay at her place in Accra as we are both single women who are supportive of each other and have to share sleeping quarters?

The Bill is Influenced by Sinister Western Agendas:

- The kinds of American groups who support it are not friends of Africa or Ghana.

- - Many are actually white supremacists.

- - It strikes me as likely that there's an agenda to turn Africa anti-gay in order to keep Africa's image as a bad, backward place full of idiotic savages who hunt their own GSOM people.

Bill is Dangerous:

- The Bill equates gay rape and consensual homosexual relations. That's harmful.

- It gives attackers a lower punishment than GSOM people who have done no harm.

- - There indeed should be sentencing for those who attack, abuse, discriminate

against or threaten people based on being of GSOM but these hate crimes must be treated with utmost seriousness and the victim not punished, ignored or mistreated.

- It would not get rid of gays but push them further into an "underground" culture. That results in gangs, crime, abuse, HIV and disease within their own communities (as an evildoer can "take over" and abuse and pimp the innocent majority who have nowhere safe to turn when the authorities are hostile). That's why AIDS spread rapidly in 1980's New York City.
- The ONLY safe option for society is to legalise and protect GSOMs and teach tolerance and respect.

Confusing Children:

- The Bill explicitly allows for the spread of propaganda and misleading information which would rouse fear and hatred.
- The Bill would cause more confusion to children. As a child my friend was confused that Disney princesses always married men and not once a woman. I was confused as a small schoolgirl why it would not be allowed to marry the same sex since at that age many girls and boys expressed dislike for the opposite sex.
- Children are much less likely to be confused about GSOMs than adults. It's adults who cause the confusion by failing to understand.
- Children are well aware that most people are straight and cisgender and accepting GSOMs won't change that.
- Non-straight and transgender and nonbinary children in Ghana and worldwide are actually growing up very confused and even damaged because of anti-gay and anti-trans laws and attitudes. Awareness, legalisation and acceptance actually help children.
- Many who grew up with BBC radio in the 1960's (including my father) fondly remember performances by a "drag queen" (Stage/Drag name: "Dame Edna Everage"). It didn't do them any harm!

Allyship and Kindness:

- It's inexcusable to ban treatments which transgender people choose together with their healthcare workers. Their psychologists, endocrinologists, surgeons and selves are the ones qualified to make these decisions, not politicians. Let trans people access what are currently the only treatments shown to help trans people: social transition, social acceptance, voluntary hormone therapy, voluntary surgery and psychology and voice therapy to help cope with transition and trans identity.
- - However no treatment should be forced and certainly not "conversion therapy" which is proven to be pseudo-scientific and do long-term harm.
- The Bill bans "support" even though such LGBTI+ organisations do good works by helping feed and protect homeless youth and provide an alternative "family" unit to those who have been left without family. This is how any true Christian, true Muslim or true Humanist would behave.
- - This is further evidence the Bill is against family values.
- - This will fill prisons unnecessarily
- - - and cost the nation more money wastage.

- - More people will starve on the street,
- - - experience forced marriage,
- - - be left begging,
- - - be assaulted,
- - - murdered,
- - - raped (many lesbians experience "corrective rape" which would surely only make them repulsed by men not attracted! Trans people of all gender identities get raped by straight people)
- - - and even kill themselves.

Culture:

- It is miseducated and dishonest to view homosexuality and transgenderism as "Western" "foreign" "un-African" or even "unnatural".
- Look at Russia: very white-supremacist and are they bringing in gay marriage? No! They oppress them. Therefore gayness is not "white".
- - Pre-colonial West African history makes specific references to homosexual practices. However I do not condone the aspects of these ancient cultures which molested underage boys.
- - Homosexuality is in fact seen in the animal kingdom and certainly has shown no threat to them.
- - The colonisers were the ones to pressure Africa and Ghana to adopt laws and attitudes against GSOMs. Look at the dates of their introductions!
- - African countries showed tolerance of their own GSOM people before many Western countries ever did. South Africa, Guinea-Bissau, Botswana, Cape Verde and others accept and legalise to varying degrees. To claim those countries were simply "western influenced" insults these Great African Nations.
- - GSOM people are well known to have always existed in every era and every culture. Numerous cultures least influenced by the West are actually among the most tolerant and it hasn't hurt them. For example one Indonesian tribe with 5 genders. (Male men, womanly men, in-between, manly women and female women). Native Canadian tribes see trans people as "two-spirit" and accept. In a particular Nigerian tribe, it is customary for the King to take a ritual husband. He also contains spirits of previous Kings and a Queen.
- Sometimes it is right to change aspects of a culture if they are harmful. We see that with Female Genital Mutilation (FGM).
- Making improvements to culture does not "destroy" it.
- If one does not like a Westernised LGBTI+ culture, stop rejecting Ghanaian GSOM people and allow them grow their uniquely Ghanaian version naturally such as gender transition announcement ceremonies done "African-style" etc. This will actually enrich local cultures instead of some gradual fade into carbon copies of the USA.
 - Hate is not an African or Ghanaian value
 - Prejudice is not an African or Ghanaian value
 - Ignorance is not an African or Ghanaian value
 - Uneducatedness is not an African or Ghanaian value
 - Colonial attitudes are not an African or Ghanaian value

The Bill Encourages FGM and Similar.

- Girls with a longer clitoris might be mutilated to fit paranoid, sexist social expectations.
- -There would be pressure to mutilate the genitals of intersex children to "make" them "female" or "male". This is senseless.
- - - All surgery carries risks. Genital surgery is especially risky. Some would die.
- - - You can't decide someone' else's gender by changing their genitals. Intersex is intersex. Created by nature, created by God.
 - - - - To surgically change someone's sex then later punish them for not living the gender the surgeon decided is completely nonsensical. It makes sense for most Intersex people to have both male and female traits. Whether they feel male, female, neither or both, so be it.
 - - - - Given that much of the population cannot spare money for such surgery, it will only result in infanticides and improper mutilations performed by unqualified people, causing much harm.

Religion:

- Jesus never preached against homosexuals.
- Ancient Jewish stories about Sodom and Gomorrah are likely actually about inhospitality and/or raping strangers (because in such times, a town not being hospitable meant the traveller would die in the desert). It is evident from this Biblical text that male sexual relations were viewed by the Israelites simply as "sex".
- Indeed Leviticus states "man shall not lie with man" but if one is to enforce this, then one must also carry out all the rituals in Leviticus and not mix fabrics, eat pig etc etc. And it doesn't complain about lesbian relations.
- Jesus himself complained about hypocrites and did not like religious authorities' obsession with rules.
- Jesus stated the 3 most important things as Faith, Hope and Love. The greatest of these was not Faith but LOVE. One must act first with Love towards GSOM people if one calls oneself Christian.
- - The Bill is therefore unChristian.
- "What would Jesus do?" Jesus would come to their homes, listen and dine, not create such a monstrous Bill.
- Jesus broke gender and sexuality norms and was exceptionally tolerant of others who did.
- - Jesus was an unmarried man, extremely unusual then.
- - Reference is made in the Bible to his beloved who was a man. It is not clear if it was sexual or romantic or a "best friend" nor are these ruled out but it's clear this Joseph was an exception, not an ordinary disciple.
- - He interacted with women as equals and Mary Magdelene was a primary disciple of Jesus if not the most favoured.
- - The Pope himself, although he doesn't favour Catholic gay marriage, says we should welcome our gay brothers, sisters, sons and daughters.
- - the Anglican church welcomes all including GSOMs and in some places even blesses gay couples.

- I find no reason in the Qur'an to hate or punish GSOMs.
 - Many of the Ancestors would have been involved in homosexual and transgender-like actions so one cannot disrespect them by claiming they'd all hate such things.
 - Looking at Ireland again, a non-coloniser who also overcame British occupation, friendly like Ghana, neutral and where the vast majority have faith, predominantly Christian, the Pope's visit there included families supporting a gay son or daughter as part of the Mass. When that nation voted in favour of legalising gay marriage, miracles of rainbows appeared in the sky on referendum results day in the 2 biggest cities on a rainless day, lasting exceptionally long. Rainbows also appeared similarly in parts of the US when their Supreme Court ruled similarly. I am sure that is a clear sign from God.
- Therefore Religion cannot be an excuse to condone such a Bill. Religion can actually be a good reason to stop the bill.

Economy:

- The Bill would be damaging for Ghana and her economy.
 - - Many who embraced the "year of return" may decide to leave.
 - - Fewer people would want to visit a country with such backward laws.
 - - Ghana would lose much of its friendly reputation, ruining tourism..
 - - Ghana's international image would become that of a backward, savage, dangerous country which hunts its own GSOM people.
 - - Fewer countries would want to do trade with Ghana.
 - - Many more Ghanaians, of all kinds of skills and talents will want to emigrate, causing further "brain drain".

Nature:

- Homosexuality is proven to exist in the animal kingdom.
- The natural way for heterosexual people to mate is with the opposite sex. The natural way for gay men to mate is with a gay man! Lesbians with lesbians.
 - - - I understand the initial discomfort one may feel when thinking of a gay relationship but we all feel that when something is different. It doesn't mean it's necessarily wrong. I'm sure many gays feel the same about straights but they don't go bothering straights, they accept them so deserve the same respect in return. Go to a country where everyone is white or chinese or too shy to greet you or where they eat something you'd find repulsive and you will feel that same awkwardness. It's life. Move on.
- Research is also showing that having a gay man in the family is good for the family as a whole and is likely created by nature to help survival: it means there is an extra adult to protect, guide and provide for the children and he is likely to have feminine traits which also help ensure the children are cared for.
- God created each and every person as His. We have no right to hate His creation and we are not capable of understanding His ways when he created some of His children Gay, Bi/Pansexual, transgender or Intersex.

Priorities:

- This Bill is a malignant distraction from much more important issues. No wonder Ghana has problems and foreigners see the continent as poor, corrupt and backward! Problems including but not limited to:

- - Murders seem to be ever increasing, including child murder, (seemingly for bogus or dark magic practices to "get rich quick").
- - Teen pregnancy
- - Maternal and child health
- - Drug, alcohol and other substance problems
- - Homelessness, including of children
- - Violence
- - Children out of education
- - Human, child and sex trafficking
- - Kidnappings (perhaps for illegal adoption?)
- - Unemployment and underemployment
- - Pay and Working conditions
- - Bribe culture, cronyism & corruption
- - Environmental destruction
- - Chinese Neocolonialism
- - Unfair trade and Foreign exploitation of Ghana's wealth of resources
- - Child labour
- - Modern slavery
- - Exploitation of women and girls
- - Malaria, Covid and other diseases
- - Sexism, Ableism and other forms of discrimination
- - Emigration
- - Access to healthcare, preferably free.
- - Proper infrastructure
- - etc etc.

If you really care about children, address these instead of demonizing adult same-sex couples who do consenting things together in private and people with gender difference!

Every minute and Cedi wasted on this cruel, backward Bill steals from the focus needed on these most important issues.

I in fact knew a young man who died at 18 by suicide as he feared his ethnic group would not accept he was gay or might mock him. He kept it secret but he knew he'd be expected to marry once 18. He was a classmate who made us laugh and was the first of his family to complete secondary education. What a terrible loss it has been, heartbreaking the whole family, Catholics, who would rather accept a gay son/brother than a dead one. I am quite traumatised by it. His young sister was to upset to continue schooling. Quitting at 14, "What will you do?" teachers asked. She despondently replied "Just get married". These are the kind of consequences any Bill or law against gays any GSOMs has. Anyone supporting anything anti-GSOM has innocent blood on their hands.

IN CONCLUSION:

The Protection of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill is a backward abomination which is misleading in name and degrades the rights of everyone in Ghana, all sexes, genders, orientations and all families.

It is dangerous, misleading, misguided, based on myths and prejudices and has no place in Ghana.

Thus I call on all Members of Parliament and the President of Ghana to oppose the Bill.

Written in memory of young William and in memory of all Ghanaians who have died from homophobic or transphobic hate.

Written in honour of the GSOM patriots of Ghana who continue to stand up for the human rights of GSOMs, risking their freedom, safety and lives by working for the noble principle of striving to make Ghana a better nation for all.

With Best Regards,

Yours Faithfully,

Ms S. M. [REDACTED] J. [REDACTED] (DipABRSM., HND.)